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Determining The Suitable Learning Modes for Students: Implication to Practice

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Abstract. Because of the present circumstances, we must keep looking for new ways of teaching in order to ensure that learners and next generation students is not harmed in any way and receive quality education they deserved. Results suggest that we may learn about many teaching strategies and which ones are most suited for our students based on their contexts, situations, and requirements. Results provide a basis for reflection about the pros and cons of teaching and learning modalities in basic education in this time of pandemic.

Keyword: Learning modes, learners preference, distance learning

1. Introduction

As a worldwide health concern, the COVID-19 pandemic has had an enormous influence on schooling (Mudenda et al., 2020; Sheikh, et al., 2020; Maqsood, 2021). This resulted in learning techniques being offered via distant learning by halfway through the second semester of the 2019/2020 school year (Amir et al., 2020). As a result of the COVID-19 epidemic, considerable disparities in access to technology have been exposed, including those between the rich and the poor, rural vs urban, and boys and girls, both within and within countries. Children's education at home is often facilitated through online learning platforms, which are often the most effective method for establishing some sort of learning from the beginning of the child's education. (Sepulveda-Escobar & Morrison, 2020; Dhawan, 2020). They, however, have the shortest distance to the target. In certain countries, internet access is restricted to a small percentage of the population (less than 10 percent). As a result, they need more power, a reliable Internet connection, and enough gadgets for the kids in the family, including ones with appropriate functionality and capabilities and displays large enough to accommodate their needs. The digital gap also includes a discrepancy in digital literacy, which may be more difficult to overcome than the preceding one. There is also a major gender digital divide, with women far less likely to own or have access to digital devices, as well as less chance to gain computer literacy skills (Unicef, 2020).

Amir et al. (2020) noted that students were able to adjust to the new learning techniques of full DL despite certain problems, according to Amir et al. (2020). The majority of students felt that blended learning may be adopted in the future. The present COVID-19 epidemic alters not just educational technology but also pedagogical practices in the future (Livari et al., 2020; Mishra et al., 2020; Simamora, 2020).

One area where we believe Learning, Media and Technology can and should make a more direct contribution to knowledge and practice during the COVID-19 pandemic is the shift to online and digital education formats and the rise of 'remote' forms of teaching and learning as a result of mass closures of schools, colleges, and universities. (Williamson et al., 2020; Hodges et al., 2020; Whalen, 2020). Distant education has emerged as a major issue for policymakers, education enterprises, charities, instructors, parents, and students alike during this time of pandemic politics. Educational technology has also been positioned as front-line emergency services for education, making it a matter of life and death. The journal Learning, Media and Technology has established itself as a go-to source for studies on the intersection of education and technology in recent years (Green et al., 2020; Watermeyer et al., 2020). To help educators cope with this new educational crisis, a number of other venues have provided important assistance, suggestions, and referrals to existing research from promising studies that can be accessed online. This shift to digitally-mediated remote and distance education necessitates critical assessment, however.

As a result of the pandemic's consequences, teaching techniques have and continue to be influenced. Teachers must know how to modify their approaches so that teaching and its quality aren't badly influenced by the epidemic eras we're facing, because education methods aren't immune (Verde & Valero, 2019). There is evidence to suggest that enhancing the general education curriculum with self-determination skills can help students improve their academic performance, achieve their academic and career goals, and gain access to the general education curriculum (Konrad, Fowler, Walker, Test, & Wood, 2007); they have also been shown to help students improve their academic and career readiness skills (Agran Blanchard & Wehmeyer, 2000; McGlashing-Johnson, Agran Sitlington and Cavin, & Wehmeyer, 2003 (Lee, Wehmeyer, Palmer, Soukup, & Little, 2008). Students can better participate in and advance through their general education curriculum when it has been supplemented by curriculum augmentation, a sort of curriculum modification (Wehmeyer, Lattin, & Agran, 2001). This form of curriculum change varies from another type of curriculum modification known as a curricular adaptation. This does not mean that curricula are altered in any manner; instead, they are re-presented in a way that teaches students how to solve problems, create goals, and manage their time. In addition, this course provides a wide range of tools to help students define academic and transition objectives, solve issues while working toward them, and monitor and assess the progress toward those goals (Wehmeyer, Lance, & Bashinski, 2002).

Teachers can give this type of training by using a variety of curriculum and instruction models that have been developed over the years (Test, Karvonen, Wood, Browder and Algozzine, 2000), and research has shown that many of these models are effective (Test, 2000). Meta-analysis of single subject and group study designs indicated evidence of the efficacy of teaching in promoting component parts of self-determined behavior by Algozzine Browder Karvonen Test and Wood

(2001). There is adequate evidence to support the promotion of self-determination as successful, according to Cobb et al. (2009), who did a narrative metasynthesis (a narrative synthesis of various meta-analytic studies comprising seven meta-analyses studying self-determination). In addition, a number of frequently used self-determination evaluations are referred to norms and verified (Shogren et al., 2008).

Different learning delivery modes

Students and teachers are in the same physical classroom when they participate in "presence learning." The educational benefits of this teaching method have been highlighted in previous research (Anderton et al., 2021; Garca-Pealvo et al., 2021). Due to the proclamation of a state of alarm by the government of the nation, this style of teaching approach could not be used from March to September 2020. It was reopened in September 2020, when this method of instruction became eligible. Students are increasingly preferring to learn without face-to-face interaction. Public and private universities both, used to face-to-face instruction, are adopting this concept. Some distance-based degrees and master's programs are available to students, despite the fact that the majority of their classes are held face-to-face (Ben-Chayim and Offir, 2019; Hodges et al., 2020). University degree and master's degree programs that involve non-face to face classes must adapt their standard methods to meet the new requirements of non-face-to-face teaching (Chick et al., 2020). Universities that had already gone through this transition, despite the fact that they were largely presential, were able to do it more swiftly.

Students in faraway regions can participate in distance education, which is also known as online learning, via the use of technology (Dede, 1990; Sandars et al., 2020). Students and instructors from all around the world participate in this form of education. Despite the fact that their primary structure is face-to-face, they do give students the option of distance learning and master's degree programs. Online education may be synchronous when students and teachers both log in at the same time and communicate in real time, as has been noted by a number of writers. Asynchronous teaching, on the other hand, does not necessitate the presence of both the instructor and the pupils at the same time. If the class is recorded, students can watch it whenever they want (Adedoyin and Soykan, 2020; Ali, 2020). Prior to the pandemic, this style of training was already in place and was unaffected (Hwang, 2018; Daniel, 2020). In distance education, the instructional objectives of online learning may be created because there is already an established organizational framework in place (Singh and Hardaker, 2014)

Based on different kinds of online and classroom education, this approach is a blend of the two (Lightner and LightnerLaws, 2016). Due to the ambiguity of the definition, there is no consensus on the criteria, which leads to a lack of rigor in the many forms of blended learning (Misseyanni et al., 2018; Bao, 2020). It is crucial to distinguish between the new teaching approach offered in this study, i.e., online guidance in the classroom, and hybrid teaching, mirror classrooms, blended teaching.

The "Online guide classroom" is another novel way to blended learning education presented in this study. The new reality of the epidemic has made this new technique clear. A person who has come into contact with someone who has tested positive for COVID19 should undergo a contagiousness

test and remain at home until the results are known. Students are suffering as a result of the disruptions to their classes, even when the teachers themselves have no symptoms and are healthy. When a teacher instructs from home, or another place, students must go to the college in order to participate in a live videoconference. Using this method of teaching, even if the instructor is in quarantine and may have been exposed to COVID-19, or is otherwise unavailable, pupils will not be unable to attend class, for example, because of other commitments, such as aiding a Congress in another nation.

2. Methodology

The researcher employed the normative descriptive survey method making use of a questionnaire patterned after a standardized tool measuring the students' anxiety. the researcher used the purposive and universal sampling technique. this research included the input-process-output approach. the input processes. A transmittal letter will be prepared and address to the office of the district supervisor, requesting permission to conduct the study as the request will be approved; the researcher will start to distribute questionnaires to the students through their parents. Questionnaires will be retrieved and data will be collated. Data and information with regards to the study will be treated with utmost confidence.

3. Purpose of the Study

This study provides an overview of different types of teaching methodology before, during, and after the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. This study assessed the suitable learning delivery modes of the learners in this time of pandemic. A new teaching methodology is proposed. The purpose of this study report is to share what we learned about the response to COVID-19.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1. Learner's age and gender

Learners				
Age	Gender		Total	
	M	F	f	%
18 above	0	0	0	0
15-17	24	20	44	35
12-14	36	26	62	50
9-11	13	6	19	15
6-8	0	0	0	0
total	73	52	125	100

Learners' data shows that more than half of the respondents were male with 58% while female on the other hand comprise to 42%. This indicates that there were more male than female respondents. data shows that majority of the of them were male, 62 or 50% were from the age group of 12-14, followed by 44 or 35% were from the age group of 15-17, and lastly 19 or 15% were from the age group of 9-11. This indicates that 73 or 58 were male and most of them were in the age group of 12-14.

Table 2. Learning delivery modes

Learning Modalities (DO, 012, s, 2020)	Frequency, f
Face to Face	120
Distance Learning	45
Blended Learning	94
Home schooling	78
Media Reach Learning	42
E-learning	73
Printed Module	118

The result shows the learning modalities of the students as their reference in teaching and learning process. Face to face learning garnered 120 or 96% as the most preferred learning modalities of the students, followed by 118 or 94% for the printed module, 94 or 75% preferred for the blended learning, 78 or 62% preferred for the homeschooling, 73 or 58% preferred for the e-learning, 42 or 34% preferred media rich learning, and 45 or 36% were distance learning. This indicates that majority of the students preferred face to face instructions. According to Bauer-Wolf (2019) despite the steady uptick in students' classes online, an area of the institution that many schools are investing in more, recent data shows that students still preferred in -person instruction or face to face.

5. Conclusion

The effects of the pandemic have affected and continue to affect education methods every day. The education methods are not immune to the pandemic periods we are facing, so teachers must know how to adapt their methods in such a way that teaching, and its quality, is not negatively affected. Finding shows that, learners differ on their preference on learning delivery due to their individual circumstances (such as: no internet connection for online delivery mode). Moreover, data showed that learner's preference still attached to the face-to-face learning modality.

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